

Internal Temperature and Heat Flow for Quasiparticles in Quantum Bound States

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In a previous note, it was suggested one could picture a quantum bound state as consisting of quasiparticles described by $W(x) \sum_p \sin(px)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction and $\sum_p \sin^2(px)$ the momentum probability. Here $W(x) = \sum_p \sin(px)$. Summing over p yields $W(x)W(x)$, the spatial density. Using definitions from the Boltzmann transport theory, one can calculate expressions for temperature, pressure and heat flow as a function of x . Interestingly, the temperature becomes constant in space for a harmonic oscillator ground state. The quantum mechanical ground state and statistical mechanical spatial densities are both Gaussians in this case as is the momentum density. It seems that the reason for a temperature change is the presence of $\sin(px)$ which has been argued to be associated with zitterbewegung type motion as it is present even for a quantum particle in a box with no potential.

Preliminary Consideration

In Boltzmann transport equation calculations (1), one often sees the continuity of mass equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} d(x) + \frac{d}{dx} [d(x) u(x)] = 0 \quad ((1))$$

Where $d(x)$ is the density and $u(x) = \text{Average over } v [v]$, where v is the velocity. Consider a bound type state where there is no time change in $d(x)$. In such a case, one can consider a little box with $d/dt d^+(x)$ and $d/dt d^-(x)$ cancelling, i.e. flows in and out canceling. In such a case, one can attempt to write:

$$[d(x+b)u(x+b) - d(x)u(x)] + [-d(x-b)u(x+b) + d(x)u(x)] = 0 \text{ to try to describe the two flows.}$$

$$\text{Then to first order: } \left[\frac{d}{dx} d(x) \right] u(x) + d(x) \left[\frac{d}{dx} u(x) \right] = 0$$

A solution to this equation is $d(x) = 1/u(x)$, but this is the result for a classical particle (2), not a quantum one. Thus, it seems the continuity equation (which is a mass conservation equation) does not seem to hold in this form for quantum mechanics. This is interesting because some statistical theories of quantum mechanics use ((1)) as their starting point, but deal with the time-dependent Schrodinger equation and not a time-independent one as here.

If one cannot apply ((1)) to a bound quantum mechanical state, this means one must be careful about using transport equations to describe a bound quantum state as they are based on conservation type equations, at least for the temperature 0 case. (In the literature, temperature dependent transport equations are often used to describe hot nuclei, but that is a somewhat different scenario.)

Temperature and Heat Flow

In Boltzmann transport theory, temperature T and heat flow Q are defined (1) by:

$$T(x) = .33 m \langle |v-u|^2 \rangle \text{ (for 3 dimensions)}$$

$$Q(x) = .5m d(x) \langle (v-u)|v-u|^2 \rangle \text{ with } u(x) = \langle v \rangle$$

For the quantum case, we use $u(x) = [d/dx W(x)] (1/W(x))$. This follows from the quasiparticle description $W(x) \propto \sin(px)$.

$$\text{Ave } v = 1/m \text{ Sum over } p W(x) \int p \sin(px) = 1/m W(x) d/dx W(x)$$

This is a density approach so we divide everything by $W(x)W(x)$.

Then:

$$T(x) \text{ proportional to } m [(1/W(x)) (-d/dx)(d/dx) W(x) - 2/(m^2) (d/dx W(x))^2] \quad ((2))$$

For a one dimensional problem, pressure in (1) is defined as proportional to $d(x) T(x)$

And

$$Q(x) = \text{Sum over } p W(x) \int p \sin(px) (v-u)(v^2+u^2-2uv)$$

$$= \langle 1/W (-d/dx)^3 W \rangle + 2[(1/W)d/dx W]^3 - 3 (d/dx W)/W \langle -1/W d/dx d/dx W \rangle \quad ((3))$$

$\langle -1/W d/dx d/dx W \rangle$ can be written as $E-V(x) = .5mv(x)v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the velocity in a classical problem.

Thus, in this picture, there seems to be a position dependent temperature $T(x)$, a pressure = constant $d(x) T(x)$ and a heat flow except for the case of a harmonic oscillator ground state. For that case $T(x) = T$. To see this, consider a harmonic oscillator $W(x)$ proportional to $\exp(-ax^2)$.

Then conservation of energy yields: $2a = 4a^2 ax^2 + (E-V)/2m$.

The expression for temperature yields $2m(E-V) + 4a^2 ax^2$, so $T(x) = 2a$.

It is interesting to note that in such a case, the position and momentum densities of quantum mechanics are of the same form as classical statistical mechanics. This perhaps justifies the use in calculating a temperature for quasiparticles in the first place.

Reason for Position Dependent Temperature

It seems peculiar that there be a position dependent temperature in the quasiparticle picture of a bound state. It should be noted that at each point x , conservation of energy is maintained through interference of quasiparticles:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m \text{ } f_p \sin(px)]/W(x) + V(x) = E$$

In fact, kinetic energy and $u(x)$ are determined through the interference of quasiparticles, namely $\sin(px)$ and $\sin(kx)$ adding or subtracting at a point x , because $\sin(px)$ can be positive or negative. Thus, the position dependence of the temperature seems to be due to the presence of $\sin(px)$ terms. It was argued in (3) that $\sin(px)$ models zitterbewegung motion, i.e. a particle moves back and forth while moving forward with a velocity v . It thus has different probabilities to be within a wavelength and the forward and backward motions interact with $V(x)$ with the opposite sign (it is argued). Thus, one is not dealing with the “point” particles used in Boltzmann transport theory.

Consider the average motion of the quantum quasiparticles at x_1 :
 $\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p/m \text{ } f_p \sin(px_1) W(x_1)$

At x_2 one has:

$$\text{Sum over } p/m \text{ } p \text{ } f_p \sin(px_2) W(x_2)$$

Thus, the overall weight of p/m is changing due to $W(x) \sin(px)$. It is as if at each point x , the distribution of p is changing. In classical statistical mechanics a change in the momentum distribution would also be associated with a temperature change. It seems that entropy density is also changing. Some use the formula: entropy density = $-d(x) \ln(dx)$ with $d(x)=W(x)W(x)$. We have suggested entropy density = $-\text{Sum over } p \text{ } [W(x) f_p \sin(px)] \ln[W(x) f_p \sin(px)]$. As a result, this looks like a somewhat strange picture when compared with Boltzmann transport equations. It was argued in (4), that in quantum mechanical bound states, a cycling is occurring over p momentum states governed by $\exp(iEt)$. The zitterbewegung particle is forming a resonance with the potential and this seems to drive the solution. Average kinetic energy at a point x added to $V(x)$ always yields E (energy). Thus, perhaps one cannot consider the quantum bound state to match a fluid flow problem too closely. It is nevertheless interesting to consider ideas of quasiparticle temperature, pressure and heat flow. It should also be noted that one is dealing with one particle in the quantum bound state. The quasiparticles, which are averaged to obtain average kinetic energy etc, are created at different times due to an interaction with a potential. Thus, one has to be careful when using ideas such as pressure, temperature and heat flow.

Comparison of Heat Flow with the Time-Independent Schrodinger Equation

It is possible to compare ((3)) with the time-independent Schrodinger equation, by taking the gradient of this equation:

$$d/dx (-d/dx d/dx W(x)) (1/2m) = d/dx [(E-V)W] = -dV(x)/dx W(x) + .5mv(x)*v(x) d/dxW(x) ((4))$$

Where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity obtained from $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$.

The first term in ((4)) is related to the first term in ((3)) and so heat flow in ((3)) can be written in terms of Newton's force $-dV(x)/dx$. The last term also matches the last term in ((3)) although the weight is different.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that a quasiparticle description ($W(x)$ for $\sin(px)$) of a bound quantum mechanical state can lead to a position dependent temperature $T(x)$, a pressure proportional to $d(x) T(x)$ where $d(x)$ is density and heat flow. This seems strange and might suggest there is no point in calculating such quantities based on definitions used in Boltzmann transport equation theory. In the case of the quantum oscillator ground state, however, $T(x) = \text{constant}$ just as in classical statistical mechanics. In fact, both momentum and position densities in quantum mechanics for this case match that of classical statistical mechanics. Thus, there may be a motivation to consider quasiparticles and their temperature, pressure and heat flow.

References

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